

The Behavior and Satisfaction of Tourists Affecting the Sustainable Tourism at the Amphawa Floating Market in Samut Songkhram Province

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Abstract—This research aims to study; (1) behavior of the tourists affecting the satisfaction level of tourism at the Amphawa floating market in Samut Songkhram province, (2) to study the satisfaction level of tourism at the Amphawa floating market. The research method will use quantitative research; data was collected by questionnaires distributed to the tourist who visits the Amphawa floating market for 480 samples. Data was analyzed by SPSS software to process descriptive statistic including frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and inferential statistic is t-test, F-test, and chi-square. The results showed that the behavior of tourists had known tourist attractions in the province comes from the mouth of relatives and friends suggested that he come here before and the reasons to visit is to want to pay homage to the various temples for the frequency to visit travel an average of 2-4 times and the satisfaction of the tourists in the province found that the satisfaction level of tourists in the province at the significant level of the place, convenient and services have a high level of satisfaction.

Keywords—Amphawa floating market behavior of the tourists, satisfaction level, sustainable tourism, Samut Songkhram province.

I. INTRODUCTION

FOR several years consumer satisfaction is a key to a business's success. It indicates the positive emotion and experience of consumers toward businesses. Satisfied consumers also have a propensity to repurchase and recommend products to their families and friends. To achieve consumer satisfaction, businesses must understand consumers' needs to be able to provide their products and services that meet or exceed consumers' expectations.

One of the fastest-growing segments of the tourism industry is city tourism [1]. Destination marketers make extensive efforts in marketing the city and retaining tourists to maintain their position in the marketplace. The success of destination marketing lies in their ability to compete, brand a city, understand visitor perceptions and satisfaction, provide value, and manage the total visitor experience [2].

The study of destination image reveals tourists' perception of travel destinations. Therefore, it is critical to study the destination image in order to address the tourists' expectations and satisfaction to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the destination, which later will be used to improve the destination's attributes and develop marketing strategies to compete with other businesses [1].

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Thailand is a well-known international travel destination due to its long history, rich culture, beautiful natural resources, and the hospitality of Thai people. International tourists around the world visit Thailand all year round. Among travelers from South Asia, Indian tourists are the most prevalent in Thailand. Not only is the Indian outbound traveler a substantial market, but there is also an increasing number of middle-class Asian travelers who have more purchasing power [3].

Ten years ago, the only possible landmark suggestion was the floating market at Damnoen Saduak in Ratchaburi Province in Bangkok. Today, apart from Damnoen Saduak Floating Market, which is, of course, the best known and most photogenic of all time, there are so many to choose from. They have not been hurriedly built just for the sake of tourism. Actually, they are not all new but a revival of the former local markets that had died down. The one that is no less popular among tourists and sure to be very crowded is Amphawa Floating Market in Amphawa District of Samut Songkhram Province. It's only 1.30-hour drive from Bangkok. (For those who prefer a quieter place they are advised to go to Khlong Lat Mayom or Taling Chan Floating Markets in Taling Chan instead.) It is open on Fridays, Saturdays, and Sundays from 12.00-20.00 hrs, but all shops, stalls and boat vendors will be set ready around 15.00 hrs [3].

Probably no other industry in the world has suffered more from crises than tourism. Crises can occur in many different forms, including human-caused disasters and natural disasters. Many researchers have studied the negative effects of human-caused crises. These studies have focused on the effects of the crises on tourism activities and on responses from within the tourism sector. Additional research, in the context of natural disasters, is needed [2].

A disaster can turn tourism flows away from the impacted destination not only at the time of the crisis but also in the period following it, as travelers reevaluate the destination. In fact, the magnitude of the environment disaster was so significant that the tourism industry was not only disrupted, but its survival was jeopardized. While the management of an actual crisis has become an integral part of the business activity in the tourism industry, how the industry copes with post-disaster situations has not received much attention. In addition, the tourism industry could benefit from research that establishes the role of extended theory of planned behavior in the process of selecting travel destinations.

For the reasons with the potential of Amphawa Floating Market, Samut Songkhram which has been popular with the tourists as well as government policies that support local tourism, as mentioned [4].

As a result, researchers are interested in studying. Behavior and satisfaction of tourists that affect tourism in the area Amphawa floating market to determine the real key to satisfaction or dissatisfaction happens to tourists while traveling Amphawa floating market with the difference of the level of satisfaction of tourists on market factors. The result has been a guideline in determining the marketing policy of the tourism market Amphawa addition; the results will help the business travel can be selected using factors that are effective and appropriate to the market district to satisfy happening to tourists in the tourism market, Amphawa. Samut Songkhram [3].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *The Concept of Consumer Behavior*

Consumer behavior in the literature has been conceptualized in the form of four dimensions of behavior: purchase of environmentally friendly products & service (and avoidance of environmentally unfriendly products & service), search for information, conserving behavior and supporting intent. These comprise the connotative component of the traditional consumer behavior model [9].

1. Purchase Behavior

Ecologically concerned consumers are defined as those who purchase products and services that they perceive will have a positive (or less negative) impact on the environment. Such purchase behavior includes consciously limiting the use of products made with scarce resources, attempts at conserving energy consumption, and avoiding the purchase of products with excessive packaging. Some researchers also considered behaviors in terms of their friendliness towards the environment, like buying disposable razors, aerosol sprays, and beverages in disposable containers. Other researchers define purchase behavior narrowly, to include specific behaviors such as buying a product because it has a low polluting effect and switching products for ecological reasons. For the purpose of this study, and provide the definition, which includes consciously limiting the use of products made with scarce resources, attempts at conserving energy, and avoiding the purchase of products with excessive packaging [4].

2. Search for Information

The information processing theory contains assumptions about how consumers respond to information provided by various sources, and then use the information in specific choice situations. "The basic elements of the theory are the concepts of processing capacity: motivation, attention and perception, information acquisition and evaluation, decision rules and processes, and consumption and learning. In addition, mechanisms for continually examining the environment (a scanner), and interrupting current behavior, if

necessary, and means for handling conflict are needed for the operation of the theory is influenced by three other factors: individual differences, situational influences, and effects of different types of stimuli [6].

Further, the search for information may be internal retrieval from memory or external (from Consumer Reports, retailers, friends and acquaintances). Again, the search for information may be active (when a person has a specific goal in mind, e.g. a purchase goal), or passive (e.g. when a person has no purchase goal in mind). Information is in many cases actively evaluated by customers. The particular information found may lead to interrupts or changes of goals [2].

In relation to environmentally conscious consumer behavior, search for information on environmentally friendly products comprises an important behavioral outcome. This includes, for instance, the frequency of comparing package label information, noticing and paying attention to advertisements, and talking to family, friends, and co-workers about environmentally friendly products and activities. In this study, the term search for information is used per the definition of Minton and Rose [7].

3. Conserving Behavior

Conserving behavior refers to the attempts made by consumers, to preserve the integrity of the environment after the purchase, use or consumption of a product. It includes conserving actions, particularly in terms of the disposal of the product or its packaging "environmental actions" to describe environmentally concerned consumer behavior. The actions included taking own bags for groceries, buying environmentally safe detergents, using chemical pesticides in the garden, composting yard waste, buying environmentally safe or recycled products, walking or bicycling on errands under half a mile, and contributing to an environmental organization. Conserving behavior is considered as an independent variable, as one of the dimensions of "verbal commitment," and it includes recycling of newspaper, glass, or aluminum cans, and participation in clean-up drives, and contacting a community agency to remedy pollution [8]. In this study, research will use conceptualization of conserving behavior [2].

B. *Tourists' Satisfaction*

The concept of consumer satisfaction takes a central position in marketing theory and practices. Satisfaction is a major outcome of marketing activity and service to link to attitude change, repeat purchasing, and brand loyalty. There is a considerable literature on consumer satisfaction and dissatisfaction (CS/D). The concept originally referred to goods but increasingly has been developed, through the 1980s and 1990s, towards service marketing. A number of components influence satisfaction: expectation, performance (including management, service personnel, tourists themselves, and host population), disconfirmation (the differences between expectation and performance), attribution (a consideration of the locus), emotion (current feelings), and equity (relationship of time, effort, and money for value).

Those components may act independently or interactively. One or the other may weigh more in a particular tourism situation. The study of expectation, performance, and the subsequent disconfirmation has been the dominant paradigm in CS/D studies. It involves the establishment of standards, subsequent appraisal, and comparison between expectation, performance and disconfirmation [4].

The satisfaction literature suggests that expectation reflects anticipated performance. Consumers may use different types of expectation when forming an opinion about a product's anticipated performance. Miller identified four types of expectations: ideal (can be), lowest tolerable level (must be), deserved (should be), and expected (will be). The performance associated with expectation has been used as a standard of comparison to assess disconfirmation. The performance ratings are influenced by expectations rather than by the impact of changes in performance level on satisfaction. Although it is reasonable to assume that increasing performance should increase satisfaction, the magnitude of the performance effect and disconfirmation effect has not been clarified till recently [5].

It is believed that increases in performance will have relatively little impact on satisfaction if expectations remain constant. Disconfirmation arises from a difference between prior expectation and actual performance. That is, disconfirmation is determined jointly by the combination of the expectation and performance manipulation. Oliver summarized the Expectation-disconfirmation Model as a procedure of consumers forming normative standards, observing product (attribute) performance, comparing products with their norms and forming satisfaction judgments. The model posits that consumers develop expectations about a product or a service before purchasing it. Then, they compare actual performance with their expectations. If the actual performance is better than their expectations, this leads to positive disconfirmation, which means that the consumer is highly satisfied and will be more willing to purchase the product again. If the actual performance is worse than expectations, this leads to negative. Disconfirmation means that the consumer is unsatisfied and the consumer will likely look for an alternative product for the next purchase [7].

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population and Sample

In this study population was determined the sampling for the research group of foreign tourists in Thailand and traveling in Amphawa floating market Samut Songkhram. The researchers collected data from a group of male tourists Amphawa Floating Market to complete the required number of 480 people, will analyze for sentiment. (Reliability) by testing behavior, confidence, and satisfaction. The alpha coefficients (Coefficient of alpha) of Akron City Beach, which is formulated as follows:

$$r_{tt} = \frac{K}{K-1} - \left[1 - \frac{S1^2}{Sx^2} \right]$$

where; K= the number of the test set, S12=sum of the variance of scores each, Sx2=variance of plus points.

$$r_{tt} = \frac{72}{71} - \left[\frac{1 - 35.1751}{134.5840} \right] = (1.0141) \times (1 - 0.1499) = (1.0141) \times (0.8501) = 0.8621$$

The confidence test = 0.86. The sample size for the tourists using the formula Yamane is as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

By requiring n=sample size, N=total population, e=margin of error is the acceptable set at 0.05 or 5%. Instead, the formula:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

By;

$$n = \frac{2,388,550}{1 + 2,388,550 (0.05)^2} = 399.9330$$

$$n = 400$$

B. Random Sampling

In this research, the study of the behavior and level of satisfaction of the tourists towards sustainable tourism in the province and agencies involved travel within the province. Thus, the sampling method described.

1. The sampling (Purposive sampling) as an example. The research specific organizations and individuals to perform random inquiries, including the director, the supervisor of the four agencies, the tourism center. Provincial Minister for Sport and Recreation the Tourism Authority of Thailand office Central Park Historic District, Samut Songkhram and Tourism and Business Club province.
2. Random quota (Quota sampling) to collect and behavior. The satisfaction of the tourists. Until the required number is 480 people.

C. Data Collection

For collecting data in this study, the researchers collected data from questionnaires. By inquiries from tourists who travel in space, floating market Ampawa Samut Songkhram follows:

1. The information collected samples from 400 samples tourists.
2. The questionnaire has been checked for completeness and accuracy of the data prior to analysis statistically perfect.

IV. FINDINGS

Table I indicated that tourists who come to tour Amphawa Floating Market. All 480 respondents found that most of the tourists' attention to the historic site. 47.2 per cent interest a minor in history. 32.6 percent of the landscape/site. 18.0 per cent and the other 2.2 per cent respectively.

The results are shown that statistics and the standard deviation was found the tourists Ampawa Floating Market with satisfaction the high level ($\bar{x}$ = 3.59, SD = 0.85) to

determine the factors affecting the level of satisfaction in each aspect, the level of satisfaction. Location preferences ($\bar{x}$ = 3.87, SD = 0.81) and facilitation ($\bar{x}$ = 3.44, SD = 0.87) and services ($\bar{x}$ = 3.45, SD = 0.87), respectively.

TABLE I
 THE FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE INTEREST IN THE BEHAVIOR OF TOURISTS WHO VISIT THE AMPAWA FLOATING MARKET

visitors liking	number	percent
1. history	278	32.6
2. historic Site	403	47.2
3. Landscape/Location	154	18.0
4. Others	19	2.2

TABLE II
 MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION, AND THE SATISFACTION OF THE TOURISTS AMPHAWA FLOATING MARKET

Factors that affect customer satisfaction levels	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	level of satisfaction
1. Place	3.87	0.81	great
2. Facilities	3.44	0.87	great
3. Service	3.45	0.87	great
Total average	3.59	0.85	great

V. DISCUSSION

1. The results of the tourists were mostly female age older than 25 years of post-secondary education most of the pupils / students. The level of personal income per month 5001-8000 baht and a single. This is consistent with the research of merit Orapin Bunjam [7].
2. The results of the behavior of the tourists Ampawa Floating Market known tourist attractions found Ampawa Floating Market. The telling of relatives and friends suggested that he come here before. The need to respect the various temples. The frequency of visitors to travel an average of 2-4 times and will come on Saturday and Sunday. With the use of private vehicles, the tourists then get to Ampawa Floating Market. The tourists tend to focus on the purchase of miscellaneous and spend an average of no more than 1,000 baht. And the tourists will look like on tour with a stroll through the various attractions. The place has ranged similarly. The most interesting aspect of the archaeological attractions of each site. Events held a promotional tour of the province that can attract the attention of the tourists is traditionally informed the organizers of the travel journals and major tourists mainly travel back again. This is consistent with research results [7].
3. The comparison of factors affecting the level of satisfaction of visitors to tour the province. BY general information of travelers were tourists with sex, age, and occupation, monthly personal income, and status differences affect the level of satisfaction of the tourists were not significant. It found that education levels affect their satisfaction level of facilitation of tourists significantly by a partner with the LSD (Least-significant different) the significant level of 0.05 was found that the tourists' level of satisfaction with the facilitation of travel by floating market. The next level with different levels of

0.1850, which is consistent with the research of Metta Savatelek [5].

4. The relationship between personal factors as gender, age, education, occupation, personal income per month. The status of the tourists' different behaviors known attractions of the introduction of a relative or friend. The need to travel to the temple. A number of visit 2-4 times during the day Saturday and Sunday. The use of private vehicles Focuses spending on miscellaneous expenses not exceeding 1,000 baht prefer to travel by walking. Is interested in Ruins and activities to promote tourism and heritage. To get information from travel journals. Tourism is coming back again and found that the male or female behavior do not differ much. Except to get travel information from relatives or friends recommended it. The age factor Education, career, personal income per month. Status and differences in relation to the behavior of the tourists are no different. Possibly with the province, the province has been honored with a historical and archaeological site. These are factors that make the tourists' attention and often came to visit, especially during the Saturday and Sunday. The tourists will come back again tour floating market. The behavior of different reasons, including the need to travel to the temple. The frequency is of 2-4 times the number of incoming flights Saturday-Sunday. Spend no more than 1,000 baht, possibly because of personal factors affect the decision to come together. The research, the researchers found [8].
5. The results of the analysis indicate that management of the agency in charge of tourism agencies focus on the implementation of the master development plan as well as 11 primaries. Problems in the implementation of the common are a lack of cooperation and coordination among agencies, both public and private. We also observe the lack of continuity in supervision. There were not enough personnel responsible, and there is a lack of awareness of being a good host. Insufficient budget for the development and promotion activities is observed. The promotion of tourist information and events to a group of tourists, both foreign and Thailand are delayed. These are all consistent with research results [5].

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

From this research, the researchers studied how to manage tourism agency responsible for tourism of the province were also planning the development of tourist attractions. The archaeological master plan already defined. The event promotes tourism to attract tourists to the group should take into account the needs. The tourists are important providing good hospitality impresses the audience will travel back to repeat the offense which can generate income for the people and economy [1]. The tour operator has more. However, the tourists have offered opinions on the attractions in the province when it comes to tourist attractions, is within the province as a place of interest. The atmosphere is a place to learn the history as well.

The recommendations of the tourists in the tourist province are required to improve the cleaning area attractions, temples, and baths in rivers. Trash should be set up. Add enough parking places. Prepare a clear signpost. Drinking water should be provided to tourists. More trees adorn the place arrange seating Conservation, and preservation should continue to remain the same. The reception Officers advised that should speak politely with tourists. Improving the image of the province was to provide improved transportation routes with ease. There should be more information to tourists about the province. Side or front desk staff should be trained to use English for foreign visitors, the more preferred [3]. As part of the tourists must behave as guests who visit the well-preserved regulations of each visit designated locations help cleanliness do not write any on the historic site.

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